

ISic0452

I.Sicily inscription 0452

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tablet

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Roma

Place of origin (modern)

Rome

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 3868

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 37.5 cm

Width 118 cm

Depth 4 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Florentina · pia · bona · cretianachristiana
2. dulcissimae coniugicoiugi ego Maius fec[i]
3. que · vixit · mecum a · n(nis) · XXIII · me(nsibus) IIII · di(ebus) · V
4. sinesene · nulanulla querelaquerella · sepersemper · in pacepake
5. dep(osita) non(is) · Iun(iis)

Apparatus

Text of Bivona

Translation (en)

Florentina; pious, good Christian. I, Maius, made (this) for my dearest wife, who lived with me 23 years, 4 months, and 5 days without quarrel, forever in peace. She was laid down on the Nones of June

Commentary

Ferrua believed this to be a later copy of a Roman (Urban) original

Digital identifiers:

TM 491680

EDCS 21900514

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7173 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650769>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 368

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1948.0171

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0452. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4337479>